

Generating Lung CT Scans with Conditional Score-Based Diffusion Models

António Cardoso^{1,2,3,*}, Pedro Sousa¹, Hélder P. Oliveira^{1,3}, and Tania Pereira^{1,2}

¹*Institute for Systems and Computer Engineering, Technology and Science, Porto, Portugal*

²*Faculty of Engineering, University of Porto, Porto, Portugal*

³*Faculty of Sciences, University of Porto, Porto, Portugal*

*antonio.l.cardoso@inesctec.pt

Lung CT scans are essential for diagnosing lung cancer, but the development of deep learning applications is limited by the scarcity of annotated data, given the high costs of expert labeling and privacy concerns [1]. This work explores the use of conditional score-based diffusion models [2] to generate realistic synthetic lung CT scan slices guided by lung and nodule segmentation maps.

Using a subset of the LIDC-IDRI dataset, the approach optimizes a time-informed U-Net network to progressively denoise random noise into coherent lung structures that accurately follow the segmentation maps. The conditional guidance is performed by simply concatenating the segmentation maps to the noised input of the reverse diffusion process.

During training, the model is firstly optimized to generate samples without nodule information. Then, the same model is finetuned to the introduction of nodule segmentation maps in the conditional information.

Fig. 1 displays some samples from lung-only lung-and-nodule conditioned generation.

Figure 1: Synthetic samples conditionally generated from lung segmentation areas (left) and lung and nodule segmentation maps (right).

It is possible to confirm from Fig. 1 that the generative process respects the boundaries provided by the respective segmentation maps of each sample. Moreover, the lung content in the synthetic samples resembles that of the originals’.

Future work should explore extending the method to 3D conditional generation and validate the synthetic data, for instance by incorporating it into downstream model training and assessing any resulting performance improvements.

References

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